

Yield potential

Genetic variability in anatomical root traits of Indian upland rice with reference to drought resistance

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Anatomical root traits such as size of air spaces, number and size of vascular bundles, size of xylem vessels, compactness of pith, and thickness of sclerenchymatous cell layers greatly influence yield potential and adaptability of genotypes to drought.

Root samples of 118 upland rice genotypes were fixed in formalin-acetoalcohol fixative. Fine transverse root sections were cut with a microtome (Model SP1120 SIPCON) and double-stained with safranin and fastgreen. Permanent slides were prepared and cell sizes measured.

We observed remarkable genetic variation in size of air spaces. Fifteen of the genotypes (including Bagri, Bendi, and Sakun) have small air spaces (60-90 nm), 59 have medium air spaces (90-120 nm), and the rest have large air spaces (more than 120 nm). Roots with small air spaces can readily absorb oxygen present in soil during the initial stages of drought. Genotypes with small air spaces may be useful in breeding programs for drought resistance.

We observed considerable genetic variability in number and size of vascular bundles. Thirty-one genotypes have tetraaxylery roots, 47 have pentaxylery roots, 29 have hexaxylery roots, 7 have septaxylery roots, and 4 have octaxylery roots. Small increases in xylem vessel diameter cause large drops in drought resistance. Small vascular bundles have a better regulatory mechanism than large vascular bundles. Varieties Hansraj A, Jhona 349, Sarya, Beni, Poongar, N22, and Narendra-1 have more vascular bundles with small vessels (24-50 nm)

than other varieties and can therefore withstand a drastic water deficit situation.

Pith impedes water loss through various cells and stores food under water stress conditions. Forty of the genotypes studied (including Chingudri, Dhani, Karhani, Tinpakia, and Turha) have highly compact pith and can be used for breeding drought-tolerant lines.

Sclerenchyma tissue provides strength to roots and plays a vital role in

adaptiveness to drought conditions. Genotypes varied little in sclerenchyma thickness; only N22 has two cell-thick sclerenchyma.

None of the genotypes studied have all the ideal features for drought resistance, although all have a few advantageous traits for drought resistance. Findings can be used as a basis for future breeding programs. ■

Pest resistance—diseases

A close linkage between the blast (BI) resistance gene *Pi-ta²* and a marker on chromosome 12 in japonica rice

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The BI resistance gene *Pi-ta²* belongs to the chromosome 9 linkage group on the current linkage maps. But I found the locus to have a close linkage relation to a marker on chromosome 12.

I used three genetic stocks in this research. Pi No. 4 has BI resistance gene *Pi-ta²*, which is a multiple allele of the *Pi-ta* locus. This resistance gene was introduced into the japonica line from the indica variety Tadukan. Sekiguchi-Asahi is a spontaneous mutant line with the recessive gene *sl* for the leaf spot character. The *sl* locus was reported to be linked to the *Pi-ta²* locus (with a recombination value of about 9.5%), but its chromosomal location has not been identified.

87F5-19 is a linkage tester of Kyushu University, Japan, that has a marker gene *spl-1* located on chromosome 12 and

Segregation of the genes for BI resistance (*Pi-ta²*) and leaf spot character (*spl-1*) in the F₂ population of Pi No. 4/87F5-19.*

Blast resistance	Leaf spot character		
	Normal	Mutant	Total
Resistant	212	10	222
Susceptible	5	73	78

χ^2 (linkage) = 251.426 (P < 0.001, df = 1).

shows large, reddish brown spots on leaves. The university's research group identified the *spl-1* locus using primary trisomics and reciprocal translocation lines.

In a greenhouse, seedlings of the parental lines, F₁, and F₂ were inoculated at the 4- to 5-leaf stage by spraying with an aqueous spore suspension of about 3×10^5 conidia/ml. The isolate used as the inoculum, A179-142, belongs to Japanese race 037, which is avirulent to the *Pi-ta²* gene. Disease reactions were scored about 7 d after inoculation.

The leaf spots of Sekiguchi-Asahi looked similar to those of 87F5-19 in color, size, and shape. All F₁ (n = 5) and F₂ (n = 198) plants from the cross Sekiguchi-Asahi/87F5-19 had leaf spots similar to those of the parental lines without artificial inoculation. Thus, I concluded that *sl* and *spl-1* were allelic at the single locus on chromosome 12.

Inoculated seedlings clearly segregated into resistant and susceptible classes (see table). The segregation of the F₂ population derived from the cross Pi No. 4/87F5-19 gave a good fit to a 3 resistant:1 susceptible ratio for BI resistance ($\chi^2 = 0.160$, $0.60 < P < 0.70$, df = 1), and to a 3 normal:1 mutant for the leaf spot character ($\chi^2 = 1.138$, $0.25 < P < 0.30$, df = 1). The recombination value between *Pi-ta²* and *spl-1* loci was $5.0 + 1.3$ (%) calculated by the maximum likelihood method ($\chi^2 = 2.285$, $0.50 < P < 0.60$, df = 3). Therefore the *Pi-ta²* locus was estimated to be located near the *spl-1* locus on chromosome 12. ■